

The Value of Research Methods in Literary Studies

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ABSTRACT: Most research in different branches of science (Natural and Social), including literature and art, takes its source from the objective needs of humans and society. For example, every year, world Medical scholars need to find treatments and cures for human-killing diseases.

Likewise, many countries are investigating underground resources to strengthen economies and meet the needs of their people. The texture and quality of minerals are checked, water and soil are studied for the improvement of agriculture, and all these facilities can be realized through relevant professional research.

This topic is very important to the value of literary research because if a researcher writes the history of his language's literature, there are some problems with the sources, such as: how many poets with the same name have died in a certain period? If the speeches, writings, and poems are mixed up, their names are confused, or there is doubt about their effect, research can answer all these problems; therefore, there is a need for research and investigation for the development and advancement of knowledge, science, art and literature. The purpose of the article was to show the value of research methods in literary research. In the relevant part, the use of library methods in the field of literature identification, the research definition, types, and the literal meaning terminological identification, value, and importance of the "Method" term have been pointed out.

The value of research methods in the field of Pashto literary research is very significant and important.

KEY WORDS: Literary research, Research Methods, Value.

INTRODUCTION

Research has a fundamental position for the development, strengthening, and growth of all sciences and especially literature, so it is necessary to identify and recognize the value of research methods in literary research, so that literary researchers use these methods. Use it and do your literary research on it. Many literary scholars and writers have made significant and tireless efforts to develop and enrich the Pashto language and literature, and they continue to do so in order to improve the Pashto language and literature with their knowledge (Bairagi, & Munot, 2019). This topic is very important due to its literary and research value, because everyone who does research must first be knowledgeable about the methods in order to conduct research in the same part that is seen as necessary based on the content of the research (Kothari, 2004; Oancea & Punch, 2014). My goal is to encourage a number of professional writers of our language and literature to do more literary research in the relevant field under the pretext of recognizing the value of research methods. This topic should be given full attention in all sciences and especially in literature. In addition to literature, research, and types of research, there will be the literal meaning and terminological definition of the word "method" and the value of research methods.

THE VALUE OF RESEARCH

Every research method is unique, so knowing about research methods opens the door to many other literary researches for motivated writers, and they can investigate any literary subject using the aforementioned research methods.

THE VALUE OF RESEARCH METHODS IN LITERARY RESEARCH

Research methods

Since there are different types of research, there are also different methods for research, but first of all, we must understand what the method is.

A method is a set of tools or measures that facilitate reaching the final goal and meaning, and the purpose of the scientific method is to adopt those ways and methods that save the researcher from errors and make it possible for him to reach the truth Or, in simple language, all the ways and methods used by the researcher during the study of his research problem are called methods (Williams, 2007).

The word "Method" came to European languages from Latin and then from the Greek language itself (Method), which in these languages had the meaning of procedure, status and situation. This word (method) has also made its way into our languages; it is now more widely known and used. In Arabic, Dari, and Pashto, the words style, method, tradition, and method are used as equivalents of method (Bashir et al., 2017). In order for our research work to be advanced and have good results, it is useful to choose a particular method for a research topic and continue our research in the light of that particular method. In the discussion of research identification, we pointed out that many scholars have mixed research types, methods and techniques. So, here again, we mention that the opinions scholars are different about the types of research methods, which can be shown as important and useful as follows.

1. Scientific method

The scientific method argues with scientific evidence and reasons for the investigation of all scientific topics. People used to believe that the scientific method was only used in the medical and scientific sciences, but this was later proven incorrect. So, this method can be used in the social sciences as well; every literary subject is investigated in the light of this method with scientific documentary evidence and sources, and significant results can be obtained from it. The scientific method can be used in the investigation of any subject. It is worth saying that if every literary topic is investigated, it should be investigated in the presence of authentic scientific evidence so that the results are based on scientific foundations (Rommel, 2004).

2. Historical method

This is the method that sheds light on current events and situations by examining past events. This method shows the causes, flow and outcome of the events through authentic and reliable information and describes the characteristics of the events, their relationship with other events and the latest situations in time and place. The historical method is of particular importance in the evaluation and validation of information in historical research. This method is used a lot in studying the history of literature, it indicates the reasons for the rise and fall of literary eras, and this method is also a determinant and, an informant of the period of literary creation. This method is used in writing, correcting, and comparing the histories of literature, but only on the condition that the researcher has comprehensive knowledge about the historical method, because the use of the historical method of research is for experienced researchers and strong research is a task (Mason et al., 1997; Porra et al., 2014).

3. Survey method

A survey means collecting, combining, and clarifying the necessary information for research and scientific purposes on a particular subject. The survey reflects the correct norms, principles, and rules of data collection. The survey aids in problem solving by clarifying dumb, dull, and ambiguous topics. The survey method investigates the current situation and attempts to determine the quantity and quality of the research subject (Salaria, 2012), but it is much more than that in many studies, particularly the collection of folk literature. Is taken advantage of. The survey method is better than other methods for folklore research because it has a wide area and different branches. In the survey method, two techniques are usually used the most: first, questions, and second, interviews. Questionnaires are a traditional tool for survey methods. It is said that the question was used for the first time by Horus Mann in 1847, and after that, it found a lot of tradition (Salaria, 2012; Cohen, 2002).

4. Experimental method

The experimental method is not only related to the natural and scientific sciences, but it is also used in sociology, psychology, education, and other different branches of education. The experimental method brings the research subject under strict control and is therefore more reliable than other methods. Because the experimental method avoids experiments, it is widely used in natural science research. The empirical method is commonly accepted in folklore research, which means that most folk knowledge is based on folk experiences, folk

traditions, religious demands, and so on (short story, accepted). Experiences have also shown that every literary work consists of three basic elements: education, training, and beauty. The experimental method is not only the foundation of truth in the scientific and social sciences, but it also allows most of life's affairs to be accepted, that is, issues and topics that have reached the level of confirmation through experience. No one can deny its results and existence, and it is acceptable to everyone (Kothari, 2004; Newby, 2014).

5. *Method of competence*

When we don't have our own experience on a subject, we get information from our parents, teachers, and some other knowledgeable people and solve our problem through the knowledge or experience of qualified and competent sources. There is a need to clarify that there are two types of authoritative sources: The first type of source is one for which there is no alternative, and many reasonable people are also required to have their existence and educational experiences. Like the flu, when we have a headache, we are forced to go to a doctor and trust the doctor's competence to some extent. If our radio or mobile phone breaks down, we will take it to the relevant technical manufacturer, and we will have some faith in his knowledge. We cannot find expertise in all branches of science, so the needs and problems of life force us to solve our problems through knowledge and expertise. But one thing is worth mentioning: we do not submit ourselves to the authorities; they say everything, and we blindly accept them without any reason or experience. If we do not accept a doctor's prescription, we go to another doctor, and the authorities are also tested in this way, so that we can solve our problems with reasons using our knowledge and experience (Khan et al., 2007).

The word on the street is that there is a new celebrity in town. For example, in the middle Ages, Aristotle gained so much fame that most of the disputes were resolved by his opinion. Until the Renaissance period, Aristotle's theories were considered to be the same. Famous English philosopher Bertrand Russell writes: According to Aristotle, women's teeth are smaller than men's teeth. Although Aristotle was married twice, he never tried to prove this claim by counting his wives' teeth. The subject of faith in authority (Francis Bacon) has been explained very well. horse teeth According to the preceding statements, until the 17th century, scientific problems were only demonstrated by virtue, and no one looked favorably on experience, but with the passage of time, it was demonstrated that many things are acceptable without experience. They are not, but there should be a special experience in each section so that the relevant subject can find positive results by conducting the experiment in a scientific way. This method is also significant in the literary field: if we accept the authority of a poet's poem, then we want clarity about the meaning of the poem from a careful observer and about its content from a literary analyst (McBurney, 2001).

6. *Composite, mixed or composite method*

From its name, it is clear that this method is a combination of all the research methods; the researchers use several of the above methods in their research, which is called a composite or compound method. It is important and interesting to use this method in the social sciences. The advantage of this method is that the research is conducted from a single point of view, using multiple methods at the same time, and delves into the subject to obtain accurate and detailed information. In this method, the researcher also clarifies the material related to the subject, shows the reasons, and proves it with examples (McKim, 2017). Sciences are related to each other, so it is necessary that other sciences be looked at for a subject. In addition to the special principles, culture, and requirements of the Pashto language and people, we also conducted some research on Sufism, Islam, and spirituality in order to get positive results on this topic. The advantage of the composite method is that the researcher can clarify each aspect of the subject with the help of another special method. Such a method is often used in literary research. For example, if we collect materials about our topic in the library, we can also interview an author (Bairagi & Munot, 2019).

7. *Descriptive method*

In the descriptive method, different topics are explained. This method does not refer to the causes and dates of events and issues, but the materials related to the research are explained and analyzed. This method places a high value on explanations and explanations of the subject. This method is often used in library research because it takes a topic out of obscurity and complexity and explains it well. For example, if we are talking about the characters in the novel, then the researcher will explain the first character well: who is he? What is its value and position in the novel? Therefore, it is included in literary research along with descriptive research (McBurney, 2001).

8. Reason-based (comparative) method

In this method, the researcher attempts to uncover the causes of an event or topic, that is, he examines the various reasons for the growth, development, and decline of a topic to determine why it occurred. And what are the main causes of depression?

If there is a study of Khushal Baba's comprehensive knowledge in the discussion of classical Pashto literature, then in this method, everything about him is done on the basis of finding reasons. For example, the researcher would like to know what the secret of Khushal Khan Baba's all-round knowledge is. How did he get such a great position and value in Pashto literature? In this method, the researcher is only looking for, identifying, and clarifying the causes of the subject (Earley, 2014).

9. Linguistic method

It is evident from the name of this method that all the grammatical and linguistic parts of a language are under discussion. In this method, all the issues related to a language are investigated in a comprehensive way, so that the background of the origin of a language, the relationship with other languages, the linguistic branches, and the effects of other languages on this language are continuously clarified (Snyder, 2019).

THE VALUE OF RESEARCH METHODS

Research is the foundation of positive achievements in all aspects of life, so its value and importance are as clear as the sun. And these studies have been done and are still being done thanks to the availability of the above methods. If we look at today's development of science and technology, we see that thanks to research, this weak man reached the moon and succeeded in the relevant research. Furthermore, according to medical research, doctors were able to save or improve a person's life by transferring the heart of one person to another or other parts of the body. Thanks to research, economic progress has been made, which has strengthened the world economy in an unparalleled way. Countless achievements are worth mentioning in the presence of scientific research, such as: rotating metals in the air in an optional way; determining the time; using the telephone or mobile phone; sending picture and written messages to all corners of the world; quickly identifying and treating various diseases; making medicine; improving the quality of food; and creating various amazing machines to provide human comfort and to work. Thanks to the research, there has been a very positive change in the knowledge of human beings, and there have been extensive research studies in religion, politics, literature, culture, and other fields, according to which significant and interesting results have been obtained in each field.

RESULT

If research is related to any field of science, its task and purpose are accurate investigation and reaching the truth. Research can be the cause of progress in human life, and no one can ignore its benefits, so research is the soul of the development of all sciences. The only secret of current research progress is the availability and use of research methods.

During the writing of this article, I came to the conclusion that without research, human life is incomplete and difficult, so every researcher should make good use of the above research methods for their research in order to achieve certain goals in their respective research affairs. In this article, in addition to identifying research methods, definitions, types, values, and other important topics of literature and research have been clarified in the relevant section, which is placed in the content text, and anyone can benefit from it. Because all scientific and especially literary research is conducted using these research methods, this topic should be given full attention in all sciences and especially literature, because each research is conducted using a unique method. As a result, understanding research methods allows researchers and writers to conduct many other literary studies, and they can openly study any literary topic using the aforementioned research methods.

DISCUSSION

That in the field of research and research methods, different literary scholars and researchers have worked and are doing their best; each one's effort is valuable in its own right; every work that can be done first and alone is a good achievement. There will definitely be some flaws with it.

Since scholars have different opinions about the types of research, some of them list it in two categories and others mention it in three categories, but others are of the opinion that there are many types of research as well as research methods. There are various explanations and opinions about it, such as how some call it types of research, while others refer to these types of research as methods, or how some other writers refer to them as techniques, but in my opinion, the most important thing about identifying research methods and using them in research is to consider the disagreement of the scholars in the research. Some of the writers who worked in the field of research methods expressed hope for their efforts and asked the next generation to make more efforts on this subject to overcome the previous shortcomings and accept such complete methods that are acceptable to everyone and can be used in research.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Researchers should conduct research to enrich and complete the teaching materials.
2. Researchers should give priority to these research methods.
3. Special attention should be paid to the transparency and truthfulness of research.

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Cite this Article: Shafiqullah Rahmani, Sayed Asghar Hashimi, Ehsanullah Bayan (2023). The Value of Research Methods in Literary Studies. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(3), 2036-2040